

A theoretical expression of spatial and temporal frequency-dependent energy on the Planck scale

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Abstract. On the Planck scale, the amount of energy (E_p) expressed in different forms, such as the gravitational potential energy and photon energy, is the same. Here, a theoretical expression of E_p is derived, in which the energy is expressed as the harmonic mean of weighted spatial and

temporal frequencies, i.e., $E_p = \frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi}{\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{10^{10} \text{ kg m}^{-3} \text{ s}^2}{m_p^2 \xi_p} + \frac{10^{33} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}}{f_p} \right)}$, where m_p , ξ_p , and f_p are the mass, spatial frequency, and temporal frequency on the Planck scales, respectively, whereas φ is the geometric-constant golden-ratio.

Introduction

Gravitational and electromagnetic interactions are commonly experienced fundamental interactions. On the Planck scale, the amount of these two types of energy is identical. Derived from Newton's law of universal gravitation, the gravitational potential energy (U^G) between two bodies with the masses M_1 and M_2 separated by a distance of r between their centers of mass is given by

$$U^G = -G \frac{M_1 M_2}{r} \quad (1)$$

where G is the Newtonian constant of gravitation. According to the Planck relation, the electromagnetic energy (E^h) carried by a photon is proportional to the temporal frequency (ν) of the photon:

$$E^h = h\nu \quad (2)$$

where h is Planck's constant.

The value of h has been accurately determined to the ninth significant digit and been fixed to an exact value of $6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ (kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)}$ with zero uncertainty by the Committee on Data of the International Science Council (CODATA)[1,2]. Regarding G , on the basis of 16 sets of experimental measurements of G , CODATA recommended in 2018 a G value of six significant digits, i.e., $6.67430 \times 10^{-11} \text{ (kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2}\text{)}$ [1,3], which has since been generally accepted.

Planck used G , h and the speed of light in vacuum (c) to define a system of natural units of mass (m_p), length (l_p), and time (t_p):

$$m_p = \sqrt{\frac{hc}{G}}; \quad (3)$$

$$l_p = \sqrt{\frac{hG}{c^3}}; \quad (4)$$

$$t_p = \sqrt{\frac{hG}{c^5}}; \quad (5)$$

which are called Planck units. With these units, the energy, dubbed the Planck energy (E_p), may be expressed as

$$E_p = m_p c^2 = h \frac{1}{t_p} = G \frac{m_p^2}{l_p} = \sqrt{\frac{hc^5}{G}} \quad (6)$$

showing that on the Planck scale, the amounts of the photon energy ($E_p^h = h \frac{1}{t_p}$) and the gravitational energy ($-U_p^G = G \frac{m_p^2}{l_p}$) are equal.

In a previous study [4], the derivation of the following geometry-based energetic expression is described:

$$\frac{1}{2}(G \times 10^{10} \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1} + h \times 10^{33} \text{ s}^{-1}) = -\sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i} J = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi J \quad (7)$$

in which the geometric-constant gold-ratio φ is defined as

$$\varphi = \frac{1 \pm \sqrt{5}}{2} \quad (8)$$

whose positive solution, i.e., 1.618..., is adopted. The relation

$$-\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i} = -k_B T \sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i} = -\sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i} J = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi J \quad (9)$$

defines the distribution of energy in an asymmetrically partitioned system. The asymmetric partition of this system is specified by

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} = 1 \quad (10)$$

such that a probability space is partitioned with a ratio of φ into two portions given by $\frac{1}{\varphi}$ and $\frac{1}{\varphi^2}$.

Furthermore, G calculated from h using the following rearranged form of Eq. 7,

$$G = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi^2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2} - h \times 10^{23} \text{ kg}^{-2} \text{ m s}^{-1}, \quad (11)$$

matches the accepted G recommended by CODATA in 2018, i.e., $6.67430 \times 10^{-11} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2}$ [1,3].

Below, the derivation, from Eq. 7, of a hypothetical expression of energy on the Planck scale is described. Summaries of other related studies have already been shared [5-8].

Derivation of an energetic expression on the Planck scale

For operational convenience, Eq. 7 is reformatted to

$$-\sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i} = \frac{1}{2} (G \times 10^{10} \text{ kg m}^{-3} \text{ s}^2 + h \times 10^{33} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{G}{\zeta_G} + \frac{h}{\zeta_h} \right) = \zeta_\varphi \quad (12)$$

in which

$$\zeta_G = 10^{-10} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2} \quad (13)$$

and

$$\zeta_h = 10^{-33} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1} \quad (14)$$

whereas

$$\zeta_\varphi = -\sum_{i=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi^i} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^i} = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi = 0.665 \dots \quad (15)$$

To derive an expression of photon energy (E_p^h) on the Planck scale from Eq. 12, G is substituted with

$$G = \frac{hc}{m_p^2} \quad (16)$$

which is a rearranged form of Eq. 3. A substitution of Eq. 16 into Eq. 12 yields

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{hc}{\zeta_G m_p^2} + \frac{h}{\zeta_h} \right) = \zeta_\varphi \quad (17)$$

rearranged to

$$h = \frac{2\zeta_\varphi}{\frac{c}{\zeta_G m_p^2} + \frac{1}{\zeta_h}} \quad (18)$$

To convert Eq. 18 to an expression for E_p^h , it is divided by t_p , an operation yielding

$$E_p^h = \frac{h}{t_p} = \frac{2\zeta_\varphi}{\frac{t_p c}{\zeta_G m_p^2} + \frac{t_p}{\zeta_h}} = \frac{2\zeta_\varphi}{\frac{l_p}{\zeta_G m_p^2} + \frac{t_p}{\zeta_h}} \quad (19)$$

where $l_p = t_p c$.

To derive an expression of the gravitational energy (U_p^G) on the Planck scale from Eq. 12, h is substituted with

$$h = \frac{m_p^2 G}{c} \quad (20)$$

which is a rearranged form of Eq. 3. A substitution of Eq. 20 into Eq. 12 yields

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{G}{\zeta_G} + \frac{m_p^2 G}{c \zeta_h} \right) = \zeta_\varphi \quad (21)$$

rearranged to

$$G = \frac{2\zeta_\varphi}{\frac{1}{\zeta_G} + \frac{m_p^2}{c\zeta_h}} \quad (22)$$

To convert Eq. 22 to an expression for $-U_p^G$, it is multiplied with $\frac{m_p^2}{l_p}$, an operation yielding

$$-U_p^G = \frac{G m_p^2}{l_p} = \frac{2\zeta_\varphi}{\frac{l_p}{\zeta_G m_p^2} + \frac{l_p}{c\zeta_h}} = \frac{2\zeta_\varphi}{\frac{l_p}{\zeta_G m_p^2} + \frac{t_p}{\zeta_h}} \quad (23)$$

where $t_p = \frac{l_p}{c}$.

Fulfilling the expectation that $-U_p^G = E_p^h$ (Eq. 6), the expression for $-U_p^G$ in Eq. 23 is the same as that for E_p^h in Eq. 19. It then follows that

$$E_p = \frac{2\zeta_\varphi}{\frac{l_p}{\zeta_G m_p^2} + \frac{t_p}{\zeta_h}} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{l_p}{\zeta_\varphi \zeta_G m_p^2} + \frac{t_p}{\zeta_\varphi \zeta_h} \right)} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\zeta_\varphi \zeta_G m_p^2 \xi_p} + \frac{1}{\zeta_\varphi \zeta_h f_p} \right)} = \frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln \varphi}{\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{10^{10} \text{ kg m}^{-3} \text{ s}^2}{m_p^2 \xi_p} + \frac{10^{33} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}}{f_p} \right)} \quad (24)$$

where ξ_p and f_p are the so-called Planck spatial and temporal frequencies formulaically derived from $\frac{1}{t_p}$ and $\frac{1}{l_p}$, respectively. Thus, $\zeta_\varphi \zeta_G m_p^2 \xi_p$ and $\zeta_\varphi \zeta_h f_p$ are complementary such that their harmonic mean equals E_p .

Discussion

Based on the laws of conservation of energy, and given that the amounts of photon energy and gravitational energy on the Planck scale are equal, the summation of U_p^G and E_p^h would yield $2E_p$:

$$-U_p^G + E_p^h = G m_p^2 \xi_p + h f_p = 2E_p. \quad (25)$$

Thus, numerically, E_p would equal the arithmetic mean of these two types of energy:

$$E_p = \frac{1}{2}(Gm_p^2\xi_p + hf_p) \quad (26)$$

Numerically, G differs from h not only in the magnitude by 23 orders but also in significant digits. The multiplicative complementarity both between G and $m_p^2\xi_p$ and between h and f_p together ensures that on the Planck scale, the amounts of the two types of energy are equal. Comparatively, in Eq. 24, f_p is related to energy by the hypothetical converting factor “ $\zeta_\varphi\zeta_h$ ” instead of h , whereas $m_p^2\xi_p$ is related to energy by the factor “ $\zeta_\varphi\zeta_G$ ” instead of G . Like G and h , this pair of converting-factors also differ numerically by 23 orders of magnitude, which can be calculated from the ratio of the values of ζ_G and ζ_h . However, unlike G and h , they share the same significant digits of those of ζ_φ .

Given that the significant digits of ζ_φ is the arithmetic mean of those of h and G , the converting factors “ $\zeta_\varphi\zeta_G$ ” and “ $\zeta_\varphi\zeta_h$ ” are effectively modified h and G such that they have the same significant digits. That is, the product of “ $\zeta_\varphi\zeta_G$ ” ($6.650 \dots \times 10^{-11} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2}$) is the modified counterpart of G ($6.674 \dots \times 10^{-11} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) whereas the product of $\zeta_\varphi\zeta_h$ ($6.650 \dots \times 10^{-34} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) is the modified counterpart of h ($6.626 \dots \times 10^{-34} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$).

In Eq. 24, E_p is expressed as the harmonic mean of weighed ξ_p - and f_p -dependent components. Should the two components be expressed as their arithmetic mean, the resulting mean energy would rise above E_p , i.e.,

$$\frac{1}{2}(\zeta_\varphi\zeta_G m_p^2 \xi_p + \zeta_\varphi\zeta_h f_p) > \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{\zeta_\varphi\zeta_G m_p^2 \xi_p} + \frac{1}{\zeta_\varphi\zeta_h f_p}\right)} = E_p \quad (27)$$

Note that the arithmetic mean of two unequal quantities is, by definition, greater than their harmonic mean. As it stands, one way to ensure that the mean energy of the system remains to equal E_p would be a concerted transition of the converting factor “ $\zeta_\varphi\zeta_G$ ” to G and the factor “ $\zeta_\varphi\zeta_h$ ” to h so that

$$E_p = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{\zeta_\varphi\zeta_G m_p^2 \xi_p} + \frac{1}{\zeta_\varphi\zeta_h f_p}\right)} = \frac{1}{2}(Gm_p^2\xi_p + hf_p) \quad (28)$$

or

$$2E_p = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{\zeta_\varphi\zeta_G m_p^2 \xi_p} + \frac{1}{\zeta_\varphi\zeta_h f_p}} = Gm_p^2\xi_p + hf_p. \quad (29)$$

Such expressed spatial and temporal components could manifest themselves as the gravitational energy and photon energy with their own distinct characteristics.

References

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